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“BLESSED BEYOND THE WEARINESS”

All the long hours, the workload is steep,
Yet God's provision is mine to keep.
My hands and shoulders may ache and fall,
Still, grace suffices despite it all.

In the morning I feel all things anew,
Hoping I touch the hearts of a few.
Though life makes my heart go frail,
With heads held up, I've no wish to fail.

This journey is rough, the road so narrow
Yet bliss and goal would pacify the sorrow.
For every hardship, a lesson blooms
For every tear, a purpose looms.

So though weariness finds my way,
Rest will be showered after a long day.
For in this work, compassion is my call.
A calling so noble that benefits us all.